

Trial number: ____ _

On average, how breathless have you felt in the last 24 hours?

We are interested in knowing how this drainage has affected your breathing. Please help us by marking across the line to represent your level of breathlessness every day at the same time for 1 week.

Baseline:

No breathlessness _____ Worst possible
at all breathlessness

Day 1:

No breathlessness _____ Worst possible
at all breathlessness

Day 2:

No breathlessness _____ Worst possible
at all breathlessness

Day 3:

No breathlessness _____ Worst possible
at all breathlessness

Day 4:

No breathlessness _____ Worst possible
at all breathlessness

Day 5:

No breathlessness _____ Worst possible
at all breathlessness

Day 6:

No breathlessness _____ Worst possible
at all breathlessness

Day 7:

No breathlessness _____ Worst possible
at all breathlessness

Please return this questionnaire at your next appointment.